

PETROLEUM GEOCHEMISTRY OF KUCHALLI -1 IN THE NIGERIAN SECTOR OF THE CHAD BASIN

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ABSTRACT

Kuchalli -1 well, one of the twenty-three exploratory oil wells drilled in the Nigerian sector of the Chad Basin penetrated a Cretaceous succession comprising the Bima, Gongila, Fika and Chad formations. Organic geochemical analyses were carried out to assess the source-rock potential of forty (40) selected ditch cuttings. Total Organic Carbon (TOC) content was found to vary between 0.5 – 2.0wt % (moderate to good) at a depth of 1700m and 2300m. Hydrogen Index (HI) values correlated against TOC and T_{max} values indicate gas generative potential.

Results of the investigation show that the Chad Basin has hydrocarbon source rock potential at the indicated interval. TOC of > 0.5wt% was recorded in both the Gongila and Fika shales. The Bima Sandstone and the Gombe Sandstone could serve as potential reservoir rocks.

An integrated exploration programme is recommended for use in the Chad Basin to enable a better understanding of the petroleum systems of the basin.

KEYWORDS: Chad Basin; Organic geochemistry; Petroleum; Source rocks; Vitrinite reflectance

INTRODUCTION

The Chad Basin is a broad structural depression in Central West Africa and the largest intracratonic basin in Africa (Raeburn and Brynmor, 1934), with an aerial extent of about 2,333,000 square kilometers, cutting across Nigeria, the Chad Republic, the Niger Republic, the Central African Republic and Cameroon. Roughly, one-tenth of the surface area of the Chad Basin is in NE Nigeria, referred to by many workers as Bornu Basin bounded to the West by the Northern Nigerian massif, and to the South by the Benue Trough and Biu Plateau (Fig. 1). The origin of the Chad Basin is related to the separation of the African and South American crustal blocks in the Cretaceous (Burke, 1976; Genik, 1993). Workers like Raeburn and Brynmor (1934), Carter *et al.* (1963), Barber (1965), Miller *et al.* (1968), Petters and Ekweozor (1982), Avborbo *et al.* (1986), Olugbemiro *et al.* (1997) have worked extensively on different aspects of the geology of the Chad Basin. Commercial volumes of petroleum have been discovered in Chad and Sudan within this rift system. In SW Chad, development of the Doba discovery (with estimated reserves of about 1B brls) by ExxonMobil has led to the construction of a pipeline through Cameroon to the Atlantic Coast. In the Sudan, giant fields such as *Unity 1 and 2, Kaikang and Heglig* have been discovered in the Muglad Basin (Mohammed *et al.*, 1999, 2000, Obaje *et al.*, 2004). Major sources and reservoir rocks in the Muglad Basin occur in continental Aptian-Cenomanian deposits of the Abu Gabra and Bentiu Formations respectively, which are similar to, and can be correlated with the Bima Sandstone in the Nigerian Bornu Basin. In the Niger Republic, oil and gas shows have been encountered in Mesozoic-Cenozoic sequences in the East Niger Graben, which is structurally related to the Benue – Chad – Sudan – Libyan rift complexes (Zanguina *et al.*, 1998, Obaje *et al.*, 2004). The Nigerian sector of the Chad Basin has remained an area of interest to many researchers overtime. This work is aimed at studying the source rock quality using geochemical data generated from ditch cuttings from Kuchalli – 1 well in the Nigerian sector of the Chad Basin.

GEOLOGICAL HISTORY OF THE CHAD BASIN

The geological history of the Chad Basin in Nigeria began during the Upper Cretaceous (probably uppermost Albian) when over 1000m of continental sediments constituting the Bima Sandstone were deposited unconformably on the Pre-Cambrian basement (Barber, 1965). These beds are mainly restricted to the southwestern margin of the basin. The stratigraphic units are as shown in Fig. 2. During the Turonian, there was

Table 1: Rock – Eval pyrolysis data of samples from Kuchalli – 1 well in the Chad Basin

SAMPLE	TOC (Wt.%)	S ₁ (mg/g) Rock	S ₂ (mg/g) Rock	S ₃ (mgCO ₂ /g) Rock	Tmax (°C)	HI (mgHC/gTOC) X 100	OI (mgCO ₂ /g/TOC) X 100
K-1-1500	0.11	0.01	0.08	0.98	375	73	891
K-1-1590	0.31	0.01	0.01	0.95	423	3	306
K-1-1620	0.76	0.04	0.50	1.31	418	66	172
K-1-1650	0.72	0.01	0.26	0.92	427	36	128
K-1-1680	0.75	0.01	0.18	0.72	424	24	96
K-1-1710	0.98	0.02	0.60	1.13	425	61	115
K-1-1740	0.95	0.02	0.27	0.67	423	28	71
K-1-1770	1.09	0.02	0.68	1.18	423	62	108
K-1-1800	1.45	0.04	1.88	0.82	429	130	57
K-1-1830	0.92	0.01	0.26	0.52	429	28	57
K-1-1860	0.85	0.01	0.22	0.54	429	26	64
K-1-1890	0.86	0.01	0.22	0.51	430	26	59
K-1-1920	0.80	0.01	0.22	0.52	433	28	65
K-1-1950	0.75	0.01	0.22	0.53	435	29	71
K-1-1980	0.97	0.02	0.42	0.48	427	43	49
K-1-2010	0.96	0.02	0.41	0.43	437	43	45
K-1-2040	1.45	0.06	0.51	0.36	443	35	25
K-1-2070	0.92	0.01	0.17	0.34	440	18	37
K-1-2100	0.66	0.02	0.23	0.42	438	35	64
K-1-2130	0.72	0.01	0.24	0.33	433	33	46
K-1-2160	0.63	0.01	0.18	0.31	435	29	49
K-1-2190	0.43	0.02	0.12	0.28	438	29	67
K-1-2220	0.55	0.01	0.10	0.29	433	18	53
K-1-2250	0.72	0.01	0.14	0.30	432	19	42
K-1-2280	0.59	0.01	0.11	0.29	440	19	49
K-1-2310	2.11	0.07	1.64	2.28	432	78	108
K-1-2340	1.30	0.04	1.04	1.47	428	80	113
K-1-2370	1.85	0.08	2.24	2.51	428	121	136
K-1-2430	0.25	0.01	0.09	0.44	431	36	176
K-1-2490	0.18	0.03	0.08	0.76	424	44	422
K-1-2550	0.08	0.01	0.03	0.25	344	38	313
K-1-2640	0.06	0.01	0.03	0.18	295	50	300
K-1-2760	0.07	0.02	0.07	0.23	418	100	329
K-1-2790	0.14	0.04	0.14	0.30	421	100	214
K-1-2820	0.07	0.04	0.08	0.21	297	114	300
K-1-2940	0.23	0.07	0.24	0.37	431	104	161
K-1-3030	0.41	0.11	0.87	0.54	427	212	132
K-1-3060	0.06	0.01	0.05	0.20	429	83	333
K-1-3090	0.06	0.01	0.06	0.30	427	100	333
K-1-3115	0.17	0.08	0.32	0.55	423	188	324

an extensive transgression and the Gongila Formation- a mixed limestone /shale sequence was deposited. These beds are overlain by over 530m of marine shales belonging to the Fika Formation of Turonian to Santonian age.

Towards the end of the Cretaceous (Maastrichtian), an estuarine-deltaic environment prevailed and the Gombe Sandstone was deposited with intercalations of siltstones, shales and ironstones. These sediments probably extend far east into the Chad Basin. Furon (1963) suggested that the Chad Basin was a tectonic cross-point between a NE-SW trending “Tibesti - Cameroon trough”. During the Paleocene, the Kerri-Kerri Formation was deposited in the southwestern portion of the basin around Potiskum but does not extend eastwards.

In the Pleistocene and probably during the Pliocene, the Chad Formation was deposited unconformably on the Kerri-Kerri Formation and older beds and until recent times, widespread volcanic activity occurred in the southern and central parts of the basin (Burke, 1976). The sediments are lacustrine and vary lithologically both

Table: 2. Stratigraphic Succession for the Chad Basin in Nigeria (adapted from Carter *et al.*, 1963)

Age	Formation	Lithology	Depositional Environment
Pliocene Pleistocene	Chad Formation	Clay, Sand	Continental
-----Unconformity-----			
Palaeocene (?)	Kerri-Kerri Formation	Coarse Sandstones, Clay stone, sandstones	Continental
-----Unconformity-----			
Maastrictian Campanian	Gombe Formation	Shale, Sandstones, Siltstone	Deltaic Estuarine
Santonian Turonian Coniacian	Fika Shale	Blue-Black Shales	Marine
Turonian	Gongila Formation	Sandstones, Shales	Marine Estuarine
Cenomanian	Bima Formation	Sandstones	Continental
.....Unconformity.....			
Crystalline Basement			

laterally and vertically. The formation is mainly argillaceous, but well-defined sandy horizons occur. The Chad Formation covers large areas of Borno, Yobe and Jigawa States of Nigeria and exceeds 700m in maximum thickness.

In more recent times, dune sands accumulated in the Chad Basin and several ancient dune systems may be recognized. The youngest deposits are the river alluvium and deltaic and lagoonal clay-flats that blanket wide areas to the south of Lake Chad.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 40 ditch cuttings samples of shale and sandy shale were collected from the Kuchalli -1 well at 30m intervals. All the samples were washed, pulverized and analyzed for total organic carbon (TOC) by means of a LECO - CS analyzer and pyrolyzed in a Vinci Rock-Eval 6 instrument. Samples for TOC determination were treated with HCl to remove carbonate – oxidized inorganic carbon before combustion in the LECO - CS analyzer. Selected samples were solvent extracted by means of an Accelerated Solvent Extractor (ASE) using iso-haxene and acetone in a 9:1 ratio. Asphaltenes in the extracts were precipitated by addition of petroleum benzene. The remaining maltenes were fractionated into saturated (aliphatic) and aromatic hydrocarbons (HCs) and heteroatomic compounds (NSO). The saturated HC fractions were analyzed by gas chromatography by means of a Hewlett Packard 5890 gas chromatograph fitted with a 30m HP5-MS column and Flame Ionization Detector (FID). Hydrogen was used as the carrier gas in the GC; with the oven temperature set at 80°C for 2minutes, then 4 °C/minutes to 275 °C and held for 30 minutes. Additionally, the saturated HC fractions were

analyzed by Selected Ion Monitoring (SIM) for m/z 71, m/z 191, m/z 217 and m/z 218 and in full scan mode gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS) using a Hewlett Packard 5890 gas chromatograph equipped with a 30m HP5-MS column and coupled to a Hewlett Packard 5972 mass spectrometer. Helium was used as the carrier gas and the oven temperature was held at 80 °C for 2 minutes within a gradient of 4 °C/minute to 290 °C, held for 30 minutes with a total run time of 90 minutes.

Fig. 1. Schematic geological map of Nigeria showing the location of the Nigerian sector of the Chad Basin and the relationship to other inland basins (Modified after Obaje *et al.*, 2004)

RESULTS

The results are as presented in Table 1 Figures 2, 3, and 4.

DISCUSSION

The adoption of Rock - Eval pyrolysis in the estimation of the hydrocarbon generative potential of prospective source rocks is a major yardstick for getting information about their organic matter type, quality and thermal maturity, while vitrinite reflectance is regarded to be one of the most powerful paleogeothermometers (Price, 1983). Though, the reflectance of vitrinite may be facies dependant, it is not metamorphic retrograde in its behaviour, recording only the maximum temperature to which sediments have been subjected, which is a function of time and temperature of burial, as well as an indicator of thermal maturity (Tissot and Welte, 1984).

The pyrolysis results (Table 1 and Fig. 3) show that TOC values range from moderate (0.5%wt) to good (2.0%wt). The Hydrogen Index values (HI) range from 0 -50mgS₂/gTOC in Kuchalli - 1 well at depths of 1700m - 2300m and 2700m - 3100m respectively. These are typical values for Type III and IV organic matter (Peters, 1986; Langford and Blanc - Valleron, 1990; Bordenavae *et al.*, 1993; Olugbemiro *et al.*, 1997; Obaje *et al.*, 2004).

T_{max} values, particularly in the interval 1700m - 2300m, and 2700m -3100m fall within a range of 430 - 460°C which correspond to early mature – peak mature conditions (oil window) (Fig. 3). T_{max} values are inconsistent, partly due to small and ill-defined S₂ peaks. Tmax increases regularly with depth, except where unconformities, faults, changes in geothermal gradients and contamination from migrated oils cause variations (Obaje *et al.*, 2004), which may also derive from drilling mud. Again, the presence of complex faults pattern within the Chad Basin could be seen as a cause of the irregularity in the T_{max} disposition.

A Vitrinite Reflectance (VR) value of 0.5% is generally considered to be the beginning of oil generation for shales, although this boundary being a function of the composition of the organic matter. Furthermore, the rate of transformation is not sharp (Tissot and Welte, 1984). Bertrand *et al.* (1993) noted that the threshold of the “oil window” corresponding to significant generation of hydrocarbons for Type III organic matter can be defined at VR% = 0.65%. It is worth to note that the generation of petroleum, as well as being controlled by the type and richness of the organic matter present, is also dependent on temperature and time, temperature being more significant (Teichmüller, 1987). For Type III organic matter, the probability of gas generation is higher than oil generation (Monnier *et al.*, 1983; Cole *et al.*, 1994; Mukhopadhyay *et al.*, 1985). Mukhopadhyay *et al.* (1985) emphasized that VR% values between 0.8% and 1.0% represent the peak oil generation interval for Type III organic matter, and 1.0 – 1.5% correspondingly represent the peak for gas generation. From our analyses, and as presented in Table 1 and Figures 3 & 4 it can be seen that Kuchalli - 1 well has optimal interval for gas generation where the required VR% values range between 0.78 – 1.34%. Olugbemiro *et al.* (1997) in their studies indicated that “oil widow” occurs at depths of 1,270m - 2,600m in the Kanadi - 1 well and 1,985 – 3,690m in Albarka - 1 well respectively.

These values are not far from those proposed by Genik (1993), who suggested that the “oil windows” in the West African Rift Subsystems extend from around 2,500 to 4,000m. Thomas (1996) estimated the threshold of the “oil window” in the Chad Basin in Nigeria to be at a depth of 2,000m, or just below the intra – Maastrichtian unconformity.

Vitrinite reflectance (VR%) range for Kuchalli -1 well is 0.78 - 1.34 VR% at a depth interval of 1500m to 3000m indicating that the investigated interval represents the oil window. It is worth noting that the VR% values

Fig. 4. Modified Van Krevelen Diagram of Samples from Kuchalli -1 Well

increase steadily with depth and is more reliable in determining the maturity of organic matter in the Chad Basin than T_{max} , which reflects the kinetics properties of the generative part of the organic matter.

The Chad Basin provides possible source rocks, reservoir beds, and the structural environment required for the formation of petroleum. One potential source rock is the marine Fika Shale, the blue-black varieties indicating reducing conditions, overlain by the estuarine-deltaic strata of the Gombe Sandstone, which could serve as potential reservoir beds. The subsequent folding of the Cretaceous strata into large-scale anticlines and synclines is expected to result in favorable traps.

Generally, in the Chad Basin, source rocks occur mainly in the Gongila Formation and in the Fika Shales (Petters and Ekweozor; 1982, Obaje *et al.*, 2004). Reservoir lithologies may be provided by shelf sandstones facies in the same Gongila and Fika formations and in the Gombe Sandstone, where deposited. Santonian and Maastrichtian deformations which were quite intense in the Benue Trough (Benkhelil, 1989) also affected many parts of the Chad Basin. Rapid facies changes are also characteristic of the successions. Traps are therefore likely to be a combination of structural and stratigraphic. Juxtaposition of sandstone facies against shaley source rocks as a result of block faulting that produced numerous horst and graben structures in this basin can provide good drainage for generated hydrocarbons as suggested by Obaje *et al.* (2004).

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